

The Influence of Industrial Work Practice Experience on Entrepreneurial Interest in Students of Automotive Mechanical Engineering Expertise Program SMK Texmaco Pernalang

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ABSTRACT: Prakerin or Industrial Work Practice is an educational, training, and learning activity for Vocational High School (SMK) students conducted in the business world or the industrial world related to student competence in accordance with the field mastered. The purpose of this study is to determine whether there is an effect of work experience in the industry (Prakerin) on interest in entrepreneurship and how much influence. The subjects of this study include only class students. Where there are 88 students (2classes), of which 44 students are used as a test and 44 other students as a research sample.

KEYWORDS: Industrial Work Practices, Business World, Industrial World, Interest in Entrepreneurship

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is one of the developing countries that is currently actively building all sectors of development, especially the industrial sector. Given the current situation, finding a job is very difficult, causing children who graduate from SMK who do not continue to college to find it difficult to get a job, thus increasing the number of unemployed. The renewal in the world of education carried out by the Ministry of National Education through the Directorate General of Basic and Secondary Education is to publish the Outlines of the Education and Training Program (GBPP) for the SMK curriculum and the 2004 edition of the SMK Curriculum Implementation Guidelines which adhere to the following principles, namely dual-based programs. Dual system education is a form of professional expertise education that combines systematically and synchronously educational programs in schools and mastery of skills obtained through direct learning activities in the world of work directed to achieve certain skills (Depdikbud, 1994: 35). In order to realize this dual system education, one of the efforts that can be made is through industrial work practice, which is an educational activity and work training by developing abilities, skills and professions in the workplace according to the field of study or major of each student.

The experience gained when doing industrial work practices will indirectly accelerate the transition of students from school to the industrial world, in addition to learning how to get a job as well as learning how to have a job that is relevant to talents and interests. Because talent and interest will encourage individuals to focus attention and increase mental activity and activities that

are in accordance with their interests. Experience in this case is the experience gained after carrying out industrial work practices, this work experience will determine students' interest in entrepreneurship because in the industry students are taught to work with their own abilities so that they will be independent. The problem faced by the world of education, especially Vocational High Schools (SMK), is the low absorption of SMK graduates into the world of work. Ideally, nationally, SMK graduates who can directly enter the workforce are around 80-85%, while so far only 61% have been absorbed. In 2006, there were 628,285 SMK graduates in Indonesia, but only 385,986 graduates or around 61.43% were absorbed into the workforce.

SMK Texmaco Pernalang is a vocational high school established by the Texmaco Science and Technology Development Center Foundation. Industrial work practice activities are carried out by grade XI students at the end of semester IV. With such conditions, it is expected that after students carry out industrial work practices, they will have more mature skills and mental readiness to enter the entrepreneurial world. This study aims to determine whether there is an influence of industrial work practice experience on the interest in entrepreneurship in class XII students of TMO expertise program of SMK Texmaco Pernalang in the academic year 2009/2010 and how much influence

RESEARCH METHOD

The research method used is the survey method. The method used in data collection is the questionnaire / questionnaire method. The questionnaire prepared is a

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closed questionnaire, which is a questionnaire that has provided alternative answers, this will make it easier for respondents to answer. Data analysis of the trial questions was carried out Aditya I.P., Sunyoto, Rahmat Doni W.; Effect of Practice Experience 3 ISSN: 1412-1247 with a validity test using the Product Moment correlation formula (Arikunto, 1996: 160) and a reliability test using the Alpha formula, while the final analysis used the F test. The Normality Test aims to determine whether the data to be analyzed is normal or not using the Chi Kuadrat formula (Sudjana, 1996: 273). After the data is normally distributed, then the F test is performed. F test itself aims to determine whether there is an influence or not. between the experience of industrial work practice on entrepreneurial interest in students of class XII TMO program SMK Textil Texmaco Pematang school year 2009/2010.

TMO-2 with probability sampling technique, namely simple random sampling. Based on the calculation of the validity test of the questionnaire Prakerin experience seen that 20 numbers of questions in the test 19 of which are valid and only 1 is invalid ie No.10 because it has a value of $r_{xy} = 0.038 < 0.297$ for a significant level of 5% with $n = 44$. The validity test of the questionnaire of interest in entrepreneurship shows that of the 20 question numbers that were tested 19 among them valid and only 1 invalid that is No. 39 with a value of $r_{11} 0.144 < 0.297$ for a significance level of 5% with $n = 44$.

Based on the reliability test of the questionnaire, the reliability coefficient of the Prakerin experience questionnaire is 0.786 and the reliability coefficient of the entrepreneurial interest questionnaire is 0.750. Both reliability coefficients $> r_{table}$. Thus it can be concluded that the Prakerin experience questionnaire and interest in entrepreneurship are reliable and can be used for data collection.

RESEARCH RESULTS

This instrument trial was carried out in class XII

Figure 1. Diagram of Internship Experience

The description of the practical experience based on the answers to the questionnaire from students obtained an average score of 59.8 with a percentage score of 78.74% which is in the good category. In terms of the answers to each student's questionnaire, the practical experience is obtained as shown in Figure 1.

Based on Figure 1, it can be seen that most students, namely 54.55%, have practical experience in the

good category, the remaining 43.18% have practical experience in the very good category and only 2.27% are in the poor category. This shows that 4 students have gained experience in good internships. Entrepreneurial interest based on questionnaire answers from students shows an average score of 55.6 with a percentage score of 73.15% which is in the high category

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Figure 2. Entrepreneurial Interest Diagram

It can be seen that most students, 77.27%, have an interest in entrepreneurship in the good category, the remaining 15.91% of students have an interest in entrepreneurship in the very good category and only

6.82% of students who have an interest in entrepreneurship in the less good category. This shows that students already have a high interest in entrepreneurship.

Table 1. Statistical Analysis Results

No.	Variable	χ^2_{count}	χ^2_{table}	Category
1.	Internship experience (X)	3.8854	7.81	Normal
2.	Interest in entrepreneurship (Y)	1.5246	7.81	Normal

Table 2. Analysis of Variance for Regression

Source of Variation	Dk	JK	RK	FCount	Ftable	Criteria
Total	44	137238.000				
Returns (a)	1	135975.364	135975.364			
Regressions (b a)	1	546.975	546.975	32.100	4.07	Signifikan
Residual (S)	42	715.661	17.040			

Normality Test

The data normality test is used to determine whether the data obtained is normally distributed or not. This test uses the chi squared formula whose results can be summarized in table 1. Price χ^2 for data prakerin experience (X) and data interest in entrepreneurship (Y), namely : 3.8854 and 1.5246 < $F_{table} = 7.81$ for $\alpha = 5\%$ with dk = 3. Thus it can be decided that both data in this study are normally distributed.

Regression Line Linearity Test

Test the linearity of the regression line to determine whether the data is linear or not. If the data is linear, then linear regression analysis can be used but if it is not linear, then non-linear regression analysis must be used. The linearity test of the regression line in this study used the F test with the results of $F_{hitung} = 0.924 < F_{table} = 2.06$ for $\alpha = 5\%$ with dk (14:28). Thus it can be explained that between the prakerin experience data (X) with interest in entrepreneurship (Y) is linear so that linear regression analysis can be used to test the research hypothesis.

Hypothesis Testing

In order to test the hypothesis of this study, simple linear regression analysis was used. Based on the results of the calculation, the regression equation is obtained: $\hat{Y} = 16.162 + 0.659X$. Analysis of variance for regression or F test whose results can be seen in table 2. Based on the results of the analysis of variance for regression obtained $F_{hitung} =$

32.100 > $F_{table} = 4.07$ for $\alpha = 5\%$ with dk (1:42). So it can be explained that the research hypothesis (H_a) which states "There is an influence between the experience of practical work on the interest in entrepreneurship in class XII students of Automotive Mechanical Engineering expertise program of SMK Texmaco Pemalang in the academic year 2009/2010", is accepted.

DISCUSSION

The results showed that there is a significant influence between practical internship and students' interest in entrepreneurship. class XII automotive mechanical engineering expertise program SMK Texmaco Pemalang school year 2009/2010. The form of influence that occurs is a positive influence indicated from the price of the regression coefficient is positive. This means that the better the practical experience gained by students, the higher the interest in entrepreneurship and vice versa the worse the experience gained by students in practical experience, the lower the interest in entrepreneurship.

The magnitude of the influence of Prakerin on student entrepreneurial interest is 43.32%. Thus it can be explained that prakerin activities are able to foster student entrepreneurial interest by 43.32% and the remaining 56.68% of the students' entrepreneurial interest is determined by other factors not examined in this study such as parental support, neighborhood support and support other factors.

CONCLUSION

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Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that there is a significant influence of Prakerin on the interest in entrepreneurship in class XII students of Automotive Mechanical Engineering expertise program of SMK Texmaco

Pematang in the academic year 2009/2010. The magnitude of the influence of Prakerin on the interest in entrepreneurship in students of class XII of the Automotive Mechanical Engineering expertise program of SMK Texmaco Pematang in the 2009/2010 academic year is quite high at 43.32%.

SUGGESTION

Students should seriously follow the entire internship program program organized by the school together with the world of work, especially in making maximum use of time in order to obtain a certain standard of competence by never getting bored to try to find their own solutions to every work problem encountered during Prakerin before asking the instructor, trying to complete the work of friends who are absent, and trying to provide ideas or ideas for the progress of the business at the place of practice as a provision when they graduate later, both when working for others and when establishing their own employment in the form of entrepreneurship.

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